
A TRUE PICTURE OF SOCIAL LIFE IN MAULAWI AHMAD’S PROSE

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Summary: In modern Pashto literature, Maulvi Ahmed emerged as a prominent figure despite a prolonged absence from formal education. Through a stroke of luck, he experienced rapid advancement, authoring numerous books and gaining renown as a distinguished writer.

Keywords: Prose Analysis, Social Life Portrait.

1.Introduction

Maulvi Ahmad, a Pashto writer, has explored every facet of society, vividly capturing the genuine aspirations of his people through prose. His writings notably advocate for the issues he passionately believes in.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

To date, no comprehensive study has examined the depiction of social life in Maulvi Ahmed's prose, although research may have focused on other aspects. My intention is to investigate the authentic portrayal of social life in Maulvi Ahmed's prose, aiming to provide a valuable contribution to the understanding of his work.

1.2 Research Method

In my research, I have utilized a bibliographic method, relying on credible academic sources. This paper begins with an exploration of Sufism, followed by a detailed investigation into the themes of love and Sufism as portrayed in the poetry of Maulvi Ahmad.

1.3 Significance of the Research

Maulvi Ahmed infuses his writing with themes of kindness and sympathy, enriching his prose with eloquence. Emerging from humble beginnings, he is a

socially conscious writer who deeply comprehends the challenges confronting his people. His works serve as insightful guides for navigating social life and play a crucial role in fostering societal progress

Prose is often described as the art of social life because, like art which presents physical forms, prose and literature portray a broad spectrum of societal elements: its strengths and weaknesses, highs and lows, and the intricate relationships, principles, ambitions, and desires of individuals in various forms of expression.

Maulvi Ahmed has explained in a series of prose that the key to advancing social life within a community lies in securing its comfort and peace. This is crucial as people see it as the fundamental source of happiness, well-being, and the fulfillment of rightful rights. In a society where the spirit of brotherhood is embraced and individuals extend hands of unity and cooperation, it is vital to eradicate corruption and promote happiness through empathy and kindness.

Here are a few examples of Maulvi Ahmad's prose that depict the true image of society:

Maulvi Ahmad writes:

The wise are often not deceived by the pleas of their adversaries; if they are, trouble will surely follow." There's a tale where a man traveling on a camel encountered a forest fire. In the midst of it was a large snake trapped and desperate. Spotting the man, the snake beseeched him, "If you rescue me from this fire, I promise great kindness." Moved by compassion, the man freed the snake. Yet, as soon as it was liberated, the snake hissed, "I will not leave without biting you and your camel". Maulvi Ahmed emphasizes that regardless of wealth and prosperity, every individual requires sympathy and empathy, as anxiety, grief, and pain are universal sources of suffering. Social life within a community fosters awareness among citizens about each other's struggles and circumstances.

Schopenhauer asserts, "There is no better foundation for morality than pity." He advocates that human ethics should be grounded in this principle. According to him, moral actions are those that are devoid of personal gain and are solely directed towards the welfare of others. (Al-Fat, 1378L.85).

In his writing, Maulvi Ahmed has pointed out this point in a very beautiful way by bringing out a truth in many good and moving words, that whoever gives a hand to someone, and the other side should not break the hand in the hand, because Society needs social life. In the Pashtun community, mothers also say that the solution is to train their children well, to choose the path of good behavior and good behavior. As Qiyamuddin Khadim says:

The height of the mother’s head is the genius of the son

The country is proud of the good times

(Azmon, 1391 L. 115)

Yes! Throughout life, humans continually contemplate ways to alleviate sorrows and suffering, seeking empathy and understanding. Life is a journey in pursuit of happiness, with nights spent in hope for joy. In this context, another Pashto poet, Gul Pacha Alfat, expresses:

Weep in grief, sympathize with everyone

A hundred moths burn with the cry of one candle

It is not possible for a person not to be saddened by the grief of another

It is a great misfortune if no one cries with anyone

(Benwa, 1388 L. 122 AD)

The Pashtun community also requires individuals who possess empathy and compassion, who, like moths drawn to light, extend hands of brotherhood and unity to their people. They inspire and urge society to embrace sympathy and kindness, akin to a kite that is enamored with a candle and finds satisfaction in its presence. This sentiment is encapsulated in the following words:

We want the heart that burns in sorrow

We want this red kite to burn together

(Alkozi, 1397 L. 20th)

Maulvi Ahmad established a criterion for distinguishing between good and bad based on their service and benefit to society. He regarded anything that is beneficial and useful for people in the civilized world as good, while condemning what is deemed useless or harmful. This perspective is articulated as follows:

I will hurt you for that amount

In grief, Chara Joy became a poor person

(Yosefzi Nouri, 1399 L. 178 AD)

The world is likened to a field where all human actions and deeds are seeds. Every individual's actions, whether good or bad, inevitably yield fruits that they must reap.

In this context, Maulvi Ahmad writes about the importance of patience, endurance, and tolerance in every situation. He emphasizes that patience is crucial because, as the saying goes, "the fruit of patience ripens with delay."

"The greedy are always busy, while the patient remain at rest." Maulvi Ahmad illustrates this with a story: A man walking in the desert spots a beautiful fox with clean fur. Greedily, he plans to catch and sell it for profit. He digs a pit, covers it with grass and something smelly, and waits in hiding. A bear, descending from the mountain, falls into the trap intended for the fox. When the man rushes to the pit upon hearing the bear's roar, he gets attacked and torn apart. The fox escapes unharmed due to its patience, while the man meets his end due to his greed.

As they say: Eat a little and be happy.

There is something worthy of attention in the above prose, and that is that a greedy attitude has really started in our society. Maulvi Ahmed has made constructive criticisms on all kinds of problems and social phenomena. He has done some good pictures in the section.

It is said that: There is no end of the world, even if our life is very long and a hundred years, but man is greedy, he wants more. These are all psychological desires that do not let the soul and eyes of a person die, no matter how rich a person is, he is still in a rush to increase.

It can be seen from the example that Maulvi Ahmed is telling people to leave the path of greed, if we follow the desires of the self, then it is a matter of not being able to progress in life and we will face sufferings.

They say that the truth is bitter. Telling the truth and upholding the truth is the duty of every human being to do it well, so Maulvi Ahmed, who has highlighted the

necessity of social life in his prose, is acceptable to all and to the people of the society. It is necessary to act on it. He has exhausted himself in the service of his people with sincerity and honesty and in this way, he has offered service and support to the people of the community and the people in his community. Take high steps, because the purpose of a writer is to improve and build the social ethics, cultural and economic of its society and people from every criticism.

It is clear that Allah created man with differences, the hope that comes from some good people in social life, the hope from bad people is to get rid of the past. Good works are done by those who instill humanity and justice in their minds. Such people are not only thinking about building themselves, but they also have the determination and will to build the world. Mawlawi has pointed out this point:

“There was a man who used to stand in the court of the king and used to say that do good to the good and bad will come to the bad – and a man became very angry and, in his heart, I thought that I should do something so that the king would be banned from court. A bad smell is coming from the king’s breath – the king was very angry and said how will this matter be known – the sister of the rumor said that the king called him to come close to the king, so this is a sign that he himself His mouth will be closed – King said, don’t be sad now, I will find out about this situation – and if you go away, the man called the man and invited him to his well. After he had eaten the bread, then go again, court stood on his side and said, “Do good to the good, for the evil is enough for the bad.” The man approached him, so he put his hand over his mouth so that the king would not smell the onion. The king was sure that the man was telling the truth. It was written in the letter that every time this man reached him, he should take out the halal oil and the skin, and send the oil full of kisses to me – and the order of the king was that the paper would be used without any reward. He didn’t give for the thing – when he left, he followed his sister and said to her, “Give me this paper” – the man gave him the paper, sister, go away, he gave the paper to Amir – when Amir read the paper, he became the executioner. He asked and ordered him to remove the dead body and skin of this man – denunciation said that he is doing this – Amir said that the king’s order has been fulfilled to kill this man with a

piece of paper – denunciation said to do it. The paper was meant for someone else when I brought it – Amir said that it was not written by the king who did him a dirty trick – so the executioner got up and cut off his head and cut off his skin and filled him with kisses. The king said to his brother, “Good morning, that man came again with his order and said that it is appropriate for a good man to do good to a man and not to do evil to a man because he is more than his own.” The king was surprised and said what did he do with the paper – it was a man that so-and-so asked me to give it, but I did not give it to him – it was the king who smelled bad from the breath of the king – he said that I did not say anything. No – the king said put your hand on the hat of the woman who approached me – it was because I had given onions to such and such a man, so I said that it is not possible for king to smell it – it was king Who says the truth is that the punishment for his evil will be found by himself. (Ahmed, (?) 47 AD)

If one goes to Maulvi Ahmad’s prose and reads it completely, then a picture will come out of his prose that shines like a beam in his proud Pashtun eyes and takes the reader into the world of social events. In this prose, Maulvi Ahmed refers to those people who should never dig for other brothers, because one day you will also walk this way. Like this proverb: The tilt will not reach the destination. Or like this abbreviation:

Bora will turn God into flowers

Gardener, your incomplete intention makes me cry

(Laiq, 1364 L. 73 AD)

Having bad intentions and hatred in the heart is never good for a person, because this is the cause of the misfortunes of social life.

In every country and every people in every era, there are some people who consider it their duty to express the truth and do not protect their wealth, their head, their position, but to protect the truth and the truth. All the people accept such people who break the backbone of oppression and injustice.

It Is clear that God did not create humans without wisdom, not only humans but all creatures were created for wisdom. Allah is free and pure from vain deeds. When

his creation goes astray and the main path is lost, He sends messengers to guide them so that they can guide and direct them according to the instructions of God’s heavenly books and call them to the right path.

If there are no such people in the environment, there is such darkness and darkness, that right and wrong cannot be distinguished, and service, betrayal, and injustice appear the same in the eyes of the people. Those people are worthy to be walked away with silver and gold. These are the people who don’t go after power and wealth or the owners of the state; Rather, they follow the truth and hide the facts. Everyone should know that telling the truth is a great act of worship.

Honesty and honor are the best ethics of loyalty and stability in friendships and relationships. In Pashtun ethics, honor means the continuation of friendship and relations, sacrifice, sacrifice and fulfilling the rights of friendship, is very important. In this section, Khushal Khan Khattak says:

If you eat it on your stomach, you will be disappointed

The young man who eats with the assembly

(Khattak, 1384 L. 179 AD)

It clear us think that each nation has its own society. Its basic and basic purpose is that this society is in peace, there is no hunger, there is no poverty, all the values of life are bright, bright and happy.

All aspects of Maulvi Ahmed’s personality have been fully reflected in his prose. If a person goes to the prose of Maulvi Ahmad, then he can get such a meaning from him that the ray of development of social life shines brightly and he does not want such people to live in the society who will become the cause of the destruction of the society.

In fact, the author has not spared the efforts of the society with the pen, but he has fulfilled his responsibility with full honesty.

It is necessary for a Muslim to do those things in the society, in which the pleasure of God and His Messenger (PBUH) will be obtained. It is necessary for every citizen to choose the path of development. Save yourself from the hard work of other people, because they say: There is no comfort without toil.

Maulawi Saleh Muhammad writes in this regard:

“Anyone who is attracted to something with honesty, purity and truth, can reach the end, and a wise person learns from everything.

A new young man noticed that he had taken a grain of wheat in his mouth and scratched it on the wall. In the end, he took his courage to the place of purpose. The young man looked at him in surprise and thought that the ant also reached his goal with his determination and courage, so man is better than the creatures and can do anything if he is devoted to a task, will he not reach perfection. He made a firm determination. He was attracted to the acquisition of knowledge, he gained a lot of knowledge in a short period of time, but if one is focused on truth, he can do anything.

See the decision the ant Make up your decision, my brother

(Rafiq, 1393 L. 87 AD)

In this passage, the author encourages the younger generation and society at large to strive for genuine virtue, determination, resilience, strong resolve, education, and excellence. He emphasizes that in today's society, every individual should prioritize literacy and education, asserting that acquiring knowledge is the ultimate form of beauty.

Maulvi Ahmed has presented interesting social pictures for the people's movement. He also used his pen in the same way and he hoped to serve the people through his writings.

I have reached the end of the road of life

Where did you stay Ishna where I arrived

(See, 1394 L. 120 AD)

Conclusion

After this article, it is concluded that Maulvi Ahmed has mentioned in his prose the aspects of social life which he has called the solution to the problems and sufferings of the society (sympathy, sympathy, good intention, agreement, effort) and it was also noticed that Bulbul of the Pashtun garden had some prose and social beauty. The analysis, research and description of the high standards and virtues of prose cannot be fully grasped, his writings have their own value.

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